

Weed species in rice seedling nurseries in eastern Uttar Pradesh (UP), India

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We surveyed weed species in farmers' field nurseries in Masodha village 1985-87 wet seasons. Ten nurseries were surveyed a year, for a total of 30 seedling nurseries. Each nursery was sampled twice by quadrat and the weeds found recorded.

Eight species belonging to five genera and three families were found. The most common were *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) Beauv., *Cyperus rotundus* L., and *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) pers. (see table).

Weed species found in survey of ricefield nurseries (n = 30 sites) in Eastern Uttar Pradesh.

Weed species	Family	Absolute presence of weed ^a	Consistency ^b	Frequency ^c	Frequency ^d (where present)
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) Beauv.	Poaceae	30	1.000	0.916	0.916
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	30	1.000	0.833	0.833
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Poaceae	29	0.966	0.685	0.706
<i>E. colona</i> (L.) Link	Poaceae	15	0.500	0.216	0.433
<i>Eclipta alba</i> (L.) Hassk.	Asteraceae	12	0.400	0.233	0.583
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	Cyperaceae	5	0.167	0.100	0.600
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	Cyperaceae	4	0.133	0.083	0.625
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.) Vahl	Cyperaceae	3	0.100	0.066	0.666

^a No. of sites where taxon occurred. ^b Proportion of sites where taxon occurred. ^c Proportion of quadrats in which taxon occurred, averaged for all sites. ^d Proportion of quadrats in which taxon occurred, for sites where taxon occurred.

Farmers separate the weeds from the seedlings while uprooting for transplanting. However, *Echinochloa* spp. are morphologically similar to rice

and are often transplanted with rice. These species are highly competitive. □

Effect of resource constraints on weed growth in wetland rice

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We studied the effect of resource constraints on growth of weeds. The experiment during 1986-87 wet and dry seasons had four levels of technology:

date of planting, fertilizer level, plant population, and weed control method. Treatments were laid out in a strip-plot design with four replications (see table).

The test variety was Jaya. The main field was plowed 3 wk before transplanting for the wet season crop and 1 wk before transplanting for the dry season crop. Final harrowing and leveling were done the day before transplanting.

Weed dry weights from 1-m² area were taken 60 d after transplanting (DT). Important weeds found were *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Marsilia quadrifolia*, and *Cyperus iria*.

Only date of planting significantly affected the growth of weeds (see table). Weight of weeds in plots transplanted on the normal date was lower; rice transplanted 3 wk late showed poorer growth and development. □

Growth of weeds as influenced by resource constraints.

Treatment ^a	Dry weight of weeds (g/m ²)		Yield of grain (t/ha)	
	1986-87 kharif	1986-87 rabi	1986-87 kharif	1986-87 rabi
Normal planting date [15 May (kharif); 28 Sep (rabi)]	16.88	13.60	4.0	2.1
Late planting [5 Jun (kharif); 20 Oct (rabi)]	27.81	29.25	3.1	1.6
LSD (0.05)	7.42	8.69	0.2	0.4
Recommended fertilizer (90:20:31 kg NPK/ha)	22.66	19.69	3.8	1.9
50% recommended fertilizer (45:10:18 kg/ha)	22.03	22.56	3.3	1.8
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	0.2	ns
Recommended plant population 20 × 15 cm (kharif); 20 × 10 cm (rabi)	19.84	23.13	3.4	2.0
75% recommended plant population 20 × 20 cm (kharif); 20 × 13 cm (rabi)	24.84	23.13	3.7	1.8
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns
Chemical weed control + hand weeding 40 d after transplanting (thiobencarb 2 kg ai/ha 6 DT)	23.13	20.22	3.6	1.9
Hand weeding 20 and 40 DT	21.56	22.03	3.5	1.9
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns

^a DT = days after transplanting.

Integrated pest management – other pests

Effect of carbofuran on *Hirschmanniella* spp. infestation in irrigated rice and partitioning of rice yield increase

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We evaluated different rates of carbofuran on an irrigated field that was naturally infested with *H. mucronata* and *H. oryzae* on the IRRI experimental farm. Enclosed plots 3 × 5 m and